

ISic002751

I.Sicily inscription 002751

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Francesca Prado,system

Autopsy

None

Last Change

2021-07-05 - Francesca Prado edited the text, tagged named entities and added English and Italian translation

Place of origin (ancient)

Centuripae

Place of origin (modern)

Centuripe

Provenance

Original discovery not recorded.

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Centuripe, Museo Archeologico Regionale di Centuripe

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 32 cm

Width 27 cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Στουδιῶ σε · χρηστῆ
3. χαῖρε · ἔζη σε · ἔτη · ξ □
5. λυδιαστής

Apparatus

Text after Manganaro 1994

Translation (en)

Farewell worthy Studiosos! He lived for 60 years after being a pastoral cantor.

Translation (it)

Addio, degno Studiosos. Egli visse 60 anni essendo stato un cantore bucolico.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645154

EDR 141143

EDCS 65300226

PHI 331799

URI <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic002751>

DOI [10.5281/zenodo.4387347](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4387347)

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 44.0747

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 38.0925

Manganaro, Giacomo 1963. Nuove ricerche di epigrafia siceliota. *Siculorum Gymnasium*. 16: 51-64. At 63

Ansaldi, F. 1981. Memorie storiche di Centuripe. Catania. At 319

Manganaro, G. 1994. Iscrizioni, epigrafi ed epigrammi in Greco della Sicilia orientale di epoca romana. *Mélanges de l'École Française de Rome: Antiquité*. 106: 79-118. At 103 no 17bis ph

Orsi, P. 1900. Frammenti epigrafici sicelioti. *Rivista di storia antica*. 5: 39-66. At 48 no.12

Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 59

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2021-07-14): ISic002751. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5104389>